

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 2

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 2

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№2 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2024-2>

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1. Cho'liyevich Ne'matilla Oripov HAYKALTAROSHLIK SAN'ATIDA QADRIYATLAR IFODASINI IDROK ETILISHI.....	5
2. Khurshida Narkhodjayeva, J. Ismatova TERMINOLOGICAL LEXICOGRAPHY IS A REFLECTION OF THE DEMAND OF THE TIME AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTICS.....	9
3. Saliyeva Nigora Ikromovna, Djurayev Dilshod Mamadiyarovich O'ZBEK TALABALARINING HSK 5-DARAJASI 写作“YOZUV” BO'LIMINI TOPSHIRISHDA YO'L QO'YGAN LEKSIK XATOLARI TAHLILI.....	13
4. Mamajonov Muhammadjon Yusbjonovich MULOQOT BOSQICHLARINING PSIXOLINGVISTIK TALQINI.....	22
5. Achilova Nurxon Normammedovna QADIMGI XITOIY MIFOLOGIYASIDA AJDARHOLAR VA ULARNING TURLARI.....	28
6. Mirzayeva Mahliyo G'ayrat qizi U. SHEKSPIR “OTELLO” VA M. SHAYXZODA “MIRZO ULUG'BEK” ASARLARIDA BOSH QAHRAMONLAR SHAXSIYATI VA EMOTSIONAL HOLATINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	33
7. Mohinur Baratboyevna Nizomova NUTQIY MULOQOTDA PEDAGOGIKAGA OID TERMINLAR ORQALI YUZAGA KELADIGAN “PEDAGOGIK TIL KONTAKTI” TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING TASNIFI (INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARI MISOLIDA).....	38
8. Maftuna Do'smurod qizi Elmirzayeva INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARDAGI IJTIMOIIY HIMOYA TERMINLARNING STRUKTUR TAHLILI.....	44
9. Шамситдинова Зебо Фазлитдиновна ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ В КИТАЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ ФОРМЫ ДАВНОПРОШЕДШЕГО ВРЕМЕНИ, ОБРАЗОВАННОГО В СОВРЕМЕННОМ УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ ПРИ ПОМОЩИ АФФИКСА ПРИЧАСТИЯ -GAN.....	50
10. Озодахон Мусаева АБДУРАХИМ ПРАТОВ ШЕЪРИЯТИНИНГ ЛИНГВОДИДАКТИК ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ.....	58
11. Минхожиддин Хожиматов, АБДУРАУФ ФИТРАТ ШЕЪРИЯТИДА МИЛЛИЙ ЎЗЛИК ВА ҚАЛЬ ИНҚИЛОБИ.....	67
12. Mirxodjaeva Gulrux Miralieva INGLIZ TILINI O'RGANISHDA MUXANDISLIK YO'NALISHI TALABALARI UCHUN SAMARALI ESLAB QOLISH USULLARI.....	77
13. Saidova Rayhon Bekmurodovna ZAMONAVIIY ADABIYOTDA SHE'R VA SHOIRLIK MASALASINING BADIY-ESTETIK TALQINI.....	83
14. Nazarova Dildora Ithomovna ZAMONAVIIY SHE'RIYATDA VAZNLAR RANG-BARANGLIGI.....	89
15. Farkhodova Shahzoda Umidkizi THE PRINCIPLE OF POLITENESS IN SPEECH ADAPTATION.....	96
16. Taxmina Yunusovna Mukaramkhodjayeva SEMANTIC RELATIONSHIPS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH: POLYSEMY AND HOMONYMY.....	102
17. Isoqova Feruza Shamsiddin qizi INGLIZ TILIDA SIYOSIY DISKURSNING LINGVISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	106
18. J.Ro'ziyev BO'LAJAK TASVIRIIY SAN'AT O'QITUVCHILARINING KASBIY KOMPETENSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA KOMPOZITSIYANING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI.....	111

19. Islomova Madina Asqarovna NEMIS MATBUOT MATNLARIDA KOMIZMNING TURLARINING QO'LLANILISHI.....	114
20. Hamroyeva Maftuna Rasulovna LAQABLARNING ANTROPONIMIK BIRLIK SIFATIDA LISONIY TIZIMDAGI O'RNI VA SOTSIOPRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	122
21. Dushanova Nargiza Mamatkulovna THE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER-ORDER COGNITIVE COMPETENCIES THROUGH THE PHENOMENON- BASED LEARNING APPROACH.....	127
22. Mardanova Guljahon Furqatkizi EXPRESSION OF THE CONCEPT OF "WEALTH" IN PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF UZBEK LANGUAGE..	135
23. Mardonova Sitara Mardonovna SEMANTIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE VERBS "FEORRIAN, FYRSIAN, FEORSIAN" AND VERBS OF DIRECTION, WHICH ARE INCLUDED IN 4 CATEGORIES OF OLD ENGLISH.....	141
24. Mamajonov Muhammadjon Yusubjonovich MULOQOT BOSQICHLARINING PSIXOLINGVISTIK TALQINI.....	149
25. Бўронов Назим ФЕЙК ВА ДЕЗИНФОРМАЦИЯГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШДА МЕДИАСАВОДХОНЛИКНИНГ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ.....	155
26. Narzullaeva Diyora Zayniddin kizi STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF POTTERY TERMINOLOGY IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGE SYSTEMS.....	161
27. Islombek Raxmonberdiyev Ilxom o'gli SAMYUEL F. HANTINGTON SIVILIZATSIYALAR TO'QNASHUVI PARADIGMASI IJTIMOY-FALSAFIY TAHLILI.....	167
28. Bobonazarova Gulxayo Habibulla qizi KOGNITIV TILSHUNOSLIKNING KELIB CHIQISHI VA UNGA HISSA QO'SHGAN TILSHUNOSLAR.....	176
29. Eshimova Sharofat Kenjaboyevna, Davlatova Komila Abdusattorovna KOREYS TILIDAGI METAFORA HODISASIDA KO'CHMA MA'NOLI SO'ZLAR XUSUSIDA.....	181
30. Kuvondikova Gavhar Isomiddinovna TALABALAR NUTQINING TA'LIMIY KORPUSINI YARATISHNING NAZARIY MASALALARI.....	189
31. Burxonov Utkir Farxod o'g'li ISPAN TILIDAGI ARABIZMLARNING FONETIK TASNIFI.....	197
32. Muxamedjanova Sh.B. XITOIY TILIDA INTERNET LINGVISTIKASI XUSUSIYATLARI.....	201

Jamiyatda o'z nomi bilan emas, laqab bilan yashash, salbiylik kasb etadi. Yozuvchi ham mana shu holatni jonlantirish, asar hayotiyligi, o'qishligini ta'minlash, kitobxonga mohiyatni asosli qilib ko'rsatish, qahramonlarning saviyasi, ongi, dunyoqarishini namoyon etish, ba'zi o'rinlarda yengil kulgi, ba'zi o'rinlarda esa achchiq kulgi, nafrat uyg'otish uchun qahramonlarni ba'zi o'rinlarda laqab orqali nomlashga ehtiyoj tug'iladi.

Badiiy asar tilidagi laqablar tadqiqi bir tomondan tilshunoslikning antroponimika sohasi uchun ahamiyatli bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan tilshunoslikdagi eng dolzarb masalalardan biri – badiiy asar tili va yozuvchi uslubi muammosiga ma'lum bir aniqliklar kiritishda ahamiyatga ega. Badiiy asar tilida qo'llanilgan laqablarni o'rganish orqali o'zbek tili tarixida antroponimik birliklarning o'rnini belgilash, bugungi kunga qadar boshdan kechirgan fonetik, leksik va grammatik voqeliklar hamda semantik taraqqiyoti to'g'risida ma'lum bir xulosalar chiqarish mumkin bo'ladi. Bu, albatta, masaladan ko'zlangan bir maqsad bo'lsa, ikkinchi maqsad antroponimning badiiy asar tilida qo'llanishini o'rganish bilan uning badiiy asar tilidagi ahamiyati belgilanadi va matnning lingvistik tahlili orqali badiiy matn mazmuni va g'oyasi aniqlanadi.

Antroponimning matndagi uslubiy qiymati, bajarayotgan vazifasi asar g'oyasini ochib berishdagi xizmatini aniqlash orqali shu asarning lingvostilistik xususiyati, asar muallifining individual uslubi haqida so'zlash mumkin bo'ladi.

Ko'rib o'tganimizdek til juda serqirra hodisa. Shuning uchun ham tilni xalq hayoti bilan bog'liqlikda o'rganish lozim. Buning uchun bizga birinchi navbatda badiiy asarlar yordam beradi. Badiiy asardagi antroponimik birliklar, xususan, laqablar ham mana shu millat, xalq hayoti va o'tmishidan olingani unda o'z aksini topadi. Xuddi shuning uchun ularni o'rganish va tadqiq qilish muhimdir. Bu orqali biz o'z milliy til unsurlarimiz va ulardan foydalanishda yana bir qadam oldinga siljiymiz.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, mustaqillik davri o'zbek adabiyotini lingvistik tahlil qilish orqali asarda antroponimlar shaxs va jamiyat munosabatlarini ko'rsatuvchi detal bo'la olishining guvohi bo'lishimiz mumkin. Ulardan o'rinli foydalanish asar tilini jonli xalq tili bilan yaqinlashtiradi, ularni milliylikni ko'rsatuvchi qurol sifatida baholashimiz mumkin.

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ISSN: 2181-9297

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THE DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER-ORDER COGNITIVE COMPETENCIES THROUGH THE PHENOMENON-BASED LEARNING APPROACH <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13235860>**ABSTRACT**

The current article delves into questioning the importance of developing low-order and higher-order cognitive skills. Reliance on the acquisition of ready-made knowledge can be favorable in educational institutions because of easiness and resulting in faster outcomes compared to working on developing higher-order cognitive skills demanding a laborious effort and a lot of time. Yet, it highlights the importance of developing higher-order cognitive skills because of tangible results such as knowledge construction and thoroughly thought and reasonably-made decisions due to productive thinking. It also presents a system of tasks to develop higher-order cognitive competencies through the Phenomenon-based learning approach with designed examples based on the themes presented in the curriculum of Integrated language skills. An educational technique called "Engage, Explore and Discover" is given to navigate readers' attention through the steps of cultivating higher-order cognitive skills in the domain of the Phenomenon-based learning approach, a Finnish novel educational approach in which learners acquire and construct their own knowledge-based on real observation of events, objects, people rather than simply acquiring ready-made theoretical knowledge commonly witnessed case in an educational environment.

Keywords: Lower-order cognitive competencies, higher-order cognitive competencies, Phenomenon-based learning, subject competencies, knowledge construction, in-depth research, educational technique

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YUQORI DARAJADAGI KOGNITIV KOMPETENSIYALARNI FENOMENGA ASOSLANGAN TA'LIM YONDASHUVI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH**ANNOTATSIYA**

Quyidagi maqola quyi va yuqori darajadagi kognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirishning muhimligini tadqiq qiladi. Ta'lim muassasalarida tayyor bilimlarni o'zlashtirishga tayanish mashaqqatli kuch va ko'p vaqtni talab qiladigan yuqori darajadagi kognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish bilan solishtirganda oson va tezroq natijalarga olib kelishi tufayli qulay bo'lishi mumkin. Shunga qaramay, maqola yuqori darajadagi kognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi, chunki bilimlarni qurish va samarali fikrlash tufayli puxta o'ylangan va oqilona qabul

qilingan qarorlar kabi aniq natijalar. Shuningdek, Integral til ko'nikmalari o'quv dasturida taqdim etilgan mavzular asosida ishlab chiqilgan misollar bilan Fenomenga asoslangan ta'lim yondashuvi orqali yuqori darajadagi kognitiv kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish bo'yicha vazifalar tizimini taqdim etadi. O'quvchilar e'tiborini Fenomenga asoslangan ta'lim yondashuvi sohasida yuqori darajadagi kognitiv ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish bosqichlari orqali o'tkazish uchun "Jalb et, o'rgan va kashf et" nomli ta'lim texnikasi berilgan. Ta'lim muhitida oddiy tayyor nazariy bilimlarni egallashdan ko'ra, hodisalarni, ob'ektlarni kuzatish, shaxslar bilan suhbat qurgan tarzda haqiqiy kuzatishga asoslangan o'z bilimlarini shakllantirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Quyi darajadagi kognitiv kompetensiyalar, yuqori darajadagi kognitiv kompetensiyalar, Fenomenga asoslangan ta'lim, mavzuni o'zlashtirishga doir kompetensiyalar, bilimni shakllantirish, izchil tadqiqot, ta'lim texnikasi

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РАЗВИТИЕ КОГНИТИВНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ ВЫСШЕГО ПОРЯДКА С ПОМОЩЬЮ ФЕНОМЕНО-ОСНОВАННОГО ПОДХОДА ОБУЧЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящей статье рассматривается вопрос о важности развития когнитивных навыков низкого и высшего порядка. Опора на получение готовых знаний может быть выгодна в образовательных учреждениях из-за легкости и более быстрого результата по сравнению с работой по развитию когнитивных навыков более высокого порядка, требующей кропотливых усилий и большого количества времени. Тем не менее, он подчеркивает важность развития когнитивных навыков более высокого порядка из-за ощутимых результатов, таких как формирование знаний, а также тщательно продуманные и разумно принятые решения благодаря продуктивному мышлению. В нем также представлена система заданий для развития когнитивных компетенций высшего порядка посредством феноменального подхода к обучению с разработанными примерами на основе тем, представленных в учебной программе интегрированных языковых навыков. Образовательная методика под названием «Вовлекай, исследуй и открывай» предназначена для того, чтобы направить внимание читателей на этапы развития когнитивных навыков более высокого порядка в области подхода к обучению, основанного на феноменах, нового финского образовательного подхода, при котором учащиеся приобретают и конструируют собственные знания, основанные на реальном наблюдении за событиями, предметами, людьми, а не просто на приобретении готовых теоретических знаний, что обычно бывает в образовательной среде.

Ключевые слова: Когнитивные компетенции низшего порядка, когнитивные компетенции высшего порядка, феноменологическое обучение, предметные компетенции, построение знаний, углубленное исследование, методика обучения

INTRODUCTION

Acquiring a proper and necessary skill is considered a prerequisite tool for learners in every stage of life. Equipping learners with appropriate skills and constantly enriching and refining them is the responsibility of teachers and educators in every stage of learning. From a five-year work experience in Higher Education, specifically at Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, it has been observed that the given assignments are designed for the development of lower-order cognitive competencies namely, memorization, recalling, understanding, applying, and analyzing the knowledge.

Literature analysis

According to Millrood R., and Maksimova I., knowledge is regarded as the lowest level of learning outcomes in the cognitive process, which includes knowing common terms, specific facts,

methods and procedures, basic concepts, and principles. Comprehension is seen as the meaning of the material. In traditional language learning classroom settings, comprehension and delivery of the material have become a casual practice of lessons. However, as Millrood R. and Maksimova I. highlight cognitive skills growth in the classroom relies on explicit training of lower and higher-order cognitive skills. They acknowledge that cognitive skills enable the learner to work out the four types of knowledge such as factual(facts and events), conceptual(theories and models), procedural(methodology and processes), and metacognitive awareness(awareness of ways and practices of critical thinking) [R. Millrood, I. Maksimova: 2018] These types of knowledge, based on higher-order thinking competencies including analyzing evaluating, creating, and synthesizing demand complex processes to develop and require more sophisticated cognitive processes. It has been also highlighted that ready-made knowledge acquisition appears to be more attractive to both teachers and students for delivering fast-gained results, whereas higher-order cognitive competencies give tangible results later. According to R. Millrood, I. Maksimova, learners’ cognitive skill is a functional mechanism enabling a learner to process information and produce new knowledge, creating, integrating, and utilizing the means of resolving situational challenges and problems.

Research questions

The questions expected to arise are as follows:

1. To what degree do ready-made knowledge acquisition tasks stimulate and develop learners' higher-order cognitive competencies?
2. Does phenomenon-based learning facilitate higher-order cognitive competencies? If yes? What is the degree of it? And how to measure it?

Exam requirements often result in developing subject competencies rather than cognitive skills in learners. In other words, teachers emphasize the extent of subject knowledge underestimating the significance of the knowledge construction.

Whether the tasks assigned in language learning courses including integrated language skills (presentations, discussions not based on real evidence) or whether reading comprehension tasks delivered in IELTS or CEFR exams, such as matching, true-false or multiple choice and gap-filling do facilitate higher-order cognitive competencies or not is the question which needs to be researched.

Methodology of research

The research methodology included literature analysis to establish the main points regarding the development of higher-order cognitive competencies, a system of tasks to facilitate both low-order and higher-order cognitive competencies, a teachers’ opinion poll to have a clear picture of what constitutes their assigned tasks to students, follow-up surveys from students to find out what competencies are developed as the result of daily tasks assigned in integrated language skills.

The tasks designed for the development of higher-order cognitive skills of language learners

It should be noted that higher-order cognitive competencies will be developed based on lower-order cognitive competencies.

About 50 teachers were interviewed to find out what common tasks are assigned to students

According to Tagayeva T., Begbudiyeva P., Suleymanov T., in a language learning environment, most assigned tasks for students are as follows:

The base of all tasks constitutes the following actions:

All these assignments tend to stimulate the development of low-order cognitive competencies such as knowledge acquisition, knowledge application, and knowledge presentation which can be stepping stones for the development of higher-order cognitive competencies development once the appropriate environment is realized. This learning environment can be realized through Phenomenon-based learning in which learners can develop and construct their knowledge. The tasks designed for the phenomenon-based learning environment seem to develop Bloom’s taxonomy's three upper criteria, namely analyzing, evaluating, and creating which encourages the development of higher-order cognitive skills such as knowledge construction, and identifying problems and their solutions.

Follow-up questionnaire from students regarding the list of competencies acquired in Integrated language skills:

From the presented graph, it is clear that in the competencies acquired in integrated language skills, the highest number of students responded that their speaking skills are developed while the number of students thinking that pronunciation skills are enhanced is lower than that of the previous category. There is a 1000 difference between memorizing and subject-knowing competencies while the development of thinking abilities constitutes the lowest unit.

The basis of all these assignments contributes to the development of low-order cognitive skills, highlighting the neglect of the development of higher-order cognitive skills. However, the system of tasks has been devised to cultivate higher-order cognitive competencies via the PhenoBL approach.

Engage, explore, and discover-educational technique

The system of tasks to develop higher-order cognitive skills in second-course students through the PhenoBL approach at language learning institutions.

Critical thinking and problem-solving

1. Phenomenon investigation: students are introduced to a complex phenomenon (e.g., climate change, migration patterns, technological advancements). Then, they are tasked with researching the phenomenon from several perspectives, identifying the main questions and problems to be solved.

2. Data Analysis and Interpretation: students are provided real-world data related to the phenomenon (e.g., statistics, graphs, maps). Then, they are encouraged to analyze the data, draw conclusions, and identify patterns or trends.

3. Solution Design and Evaluation: Students are tasked with identifying and evaluating various solutions to problems related to the phenomenon. They must then present their proposed solutions.

Debate and Discussion: Students are encouraged to discuss the ethical, social, and environmental implications of phenomena, analyze arguments, and form opinions.

Creativity and Innovation

4. Inventive Thinking: Students are encouraged to think outside the box and invent new products, services, or processes to address challenges related to the phenomenon.

5. Design Thinking: The students are led through a systematic approach called the design thinking process, which involves empathizing, defining the problem, ideating potential solutions, prototyping, and testing them. This approach facilitates creative problem-solving and allows for a structured and rigorous exploration of potential solutions.

6. **Storytelling and Communication:** Students are provided with the opportunity to convey their comprehensive comprehension of the phenomenon and its impact through various artistic mediums including, but not limited to, storytelling, poetry, and artwork.

Collaboration and Communication

7. **Team Projects:** To undertake an in-depth exploration of a given phenomenon, students are organized into teams. Through active collaboration, these teams engage in a comprehensive investigation of various facets of the subject matter, to achieve a shared objective. Findings and insights are shared amongst team members to ensure a cohesive and unified approach towards the study of the phenomenon.

8. **Expert Interviews:** As part of the research process, students are encouraged to conduct interviews with experts and professionals who hold relevant knowledge and insights pertaining to the phenomenon under investigation. Such professionals may include but are not limited to scientists, engineers, policymakers, or community members who have been directly impacted by the issue at hand. This approach allows for a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the topic, thereby lending greater credibility and depth to the final research output.

9. **Public Awareness Campaigns:** As an integral part of the academic curriculum, learners are required to conceive and implement public awareness initiatives that intend to enlighten and involve the community about a particular phenomenon. This entails creating diverse media forms such as posters, videos, websites, or social media content. The primary aim of these campaigns is to inculcate higher levels of awareness and knowledge about the phenomenon among the populace, thereby fostering a more knowledgeable and responsible citizenry.

Metacognition and Self-Regulation

10. **Learning Journals:** As an integral part of the PhenoBL experience, students are highly encouraged to maintain learning journals. These journals serve as a platform for students to critically reflect on their learning process, including challenges faced and successes achieved.

11. **Self-Assessment:** In order to enhance the quality of their academic work, it is recommended that students employ the use of rubrics or checklists as a tool for self-assessment. This practice enables students to critically evaluate their work and identify specific areas in need of improvement. By utilizing these evaluative instruments, students gain a deeper understanding of the assessment criteria and develop the skills necessary for achieving academic success.

12. **Goal Setting and Time Management:** Students receive guidance in establishing learning objectives, formulating strategic action plans, and proficiently managing their time to successfully fulfill project requirements.

Engage, explore, and discover technique

The academic task at hand requires students to conduct a thorough inquiry into the effects of plastic pollution on marine ecosystems. The students will be expected to delve into the various sources of plastic pollution, meticulously scrutinize data on its deleterious effects on marine life, and proffer viable solutions for reducing plastic waste and cleansing the oceans.

The academic curriculum offers students the opportunity to delve into the complexities of two significant global issues - artificial intelligence and climate change. Through a rigorous exploration of the applications of AI, students critically analyze its ethical implications and ponder the responsibility of AI development. They engage in a comprehensive study of climate data, research the effects of climate change on diverse populations and regions, and propose effective solutions for mitigating and adapting to its devastating consequences. This academic approach enables students to develop a deep understanding of these important issues and, in turn, prepares them to become informed and responsible global citizens.

Examples of Phenomenon-Based Tasks

Results

The obtained results from the teachers' opinion poll demonstrate that over half of the assigned tasks constitute rote memorization of subject content and delivery of it. Almost a quarter of tasks direct students to discuss certain topics while one-tenth of tasks are designed for having students debate. What is interesting to note is that only a small proportion of tasks encourage students to create video materials based on assigned themes.

The data from the follow-up questionnaires revealed that students' acquisition of ready-made knowledge during task completion and the development of speaking, pronunciation, memory retention, and thinking skills serve for the growth of low-order cognitive competencies such as remembering, comprehension, and applying knowledge rather than higher-order competencies including analyzing, evaluating, creating which can be accepted as an educational challenge.

Discussion

The teacher's opinion poll and follow-up students' questionnaire show that both assigned and completed tasks by students at language learning institutions stimulate the growth of low-order cognitive competencies including knowledge acquisition, knowledge appliance, and knowledge presentation neglecting the higher ones consisting of knowledge construction, knowledge generation, and resolving solution because of time consumption and strenuous efforts demanded from both teachers and learners. However, it has been highlighted that the foundation of higher-order cognition constitutes initially the development of lower-level cognition.

Conclusion

The conducted research at language learning institutions shows that a significant proportion of tasks and developed competencies facilitate the growth of lower-order cognitive competencies which can serve as the milestone for the development of higher-order cognitive competencies once a student is assigned appropriate and specific tasks designed according to the main tenets of PhenoBL approach which demands from both teachers and students to pass through the phases of Finnish novel approach to learning including critical thinking and problem-solving, creativity and innovation, collaboration and communication, metacognition and self-regulation, each comprising of certain tasks.

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7 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 2

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 2

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